

MASTER'S THESIS

Quantum Mechanics in Non-Inertial Frames: A Review

Submitted by
Anjana M.

Supervised by
Prof. E. Harikumar

School of Physics
University of Hyderabad
Gachibowli, Hyderabad, Telangana
Pin:500046

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Contents

1	Abstract	1
2	Introduction	2
3	Problem Statement	4
4	Inertial to Non Inertial Frames	5
4.1	Galilean Transformed Frame	5
4.2	Uniformly Accelerated Frame	7
4.3	In the Presence of a Potential	8
4.4	Solution of the Wave Equation	10
4.5	The Gauge Transformation	12
4.6	The Equivalence Principle	14
5	More on Non-Inertial Frames	19
5.1	Non-Inertial Frames	19
5.2	Classical Analysis	22
5.3	The Harmonic Oscillator Problem	24
6	Into Rotating Frames	28
6.1	Lorentz and Galilean Transformations in Quantum Mechanics	28
6.2	Non Relativistic Aspects of the Rotating Frame	32
6.3	Relativistic Aspects of the Rotating Frame	36
7	Spin Transport in Non-Inertial Frames	39
7.1	Generation of Spin Current in Non-Inertial Frames	39
7.2	Spin Current and Spin Conductivity	46
7.3	Spin Filter Formation	47
7.4	Induced Spin-Orbit Coupling	48
8	Conclusion	50
9	Acknowledgment	51

1. Abstract

Quantum mechanics as dealt with by standard textbooks is solely concerned with inertial frames of references while most of the physical systems are non-inertial. In this review, we examine various quantum mechanical systems to understand how the wave function, Schrodinger equation, and physical variables change as the system transitions from an inertial frame to a non-inertial one. We find gauge transformations for wave functions that aid in treating the non-inertial frames as inertial. Physical variables and effective potential may or may not adopt new forms in the altered frame, depending on the coordinate transformation.

Gauge transformations are quite similar to coordinate transformations. Analysis using classical mechanics assists in determining the type of gauge transition needed for a particular coordinate transformation. We look into the applications of phase shifts arising due to various couplings in the non-inertial transformations in quantum systems. The same is investigated from non-relativistic and low-energy relativistic limits. We also study the application of these non-inertial couplings in Spintronics, especially for the production and control of spin current which otherwise used to be a cumbersome task.

2. Introduction

Interestingly and ironically, science is said to be the study of exceptions. There may be a general theory, and on further exploration and dwelling deep into the subject matter, there might emerge exceptions or special case scenarios of the broad framework. Albeit what their names would imply, these special cases have helped immensely in leading our investigations into new realms and improving our understanding of the Universe. As it happens, these special cases are more popular than the general ones. For example, most students are introduced to the special theory of relativity before the technicalities of the general theory are brought in. Being accessible and more relatable to the real world, special theories serve as a stepping stone into the larger and rather complex framework of all-inclusive general theories. Such is the case in quantum mechanics as well.

Quantum mechanics, as dealt with by a master's student, is in fact a special case of its general framework. It is concerned solely with inertial systems while the broad theory addresses non-inertial systems. Most of the physical systems, from the trapped ions in an accelerating or rotating potential well to the expansion of the Universe, are non-inertial systems. It is quite important to approach these problems using quantum mechanical tools specific to non-inertial framework. However, the quantum mechanics in standard textbooks only prepare you to deal with inertial systems. Therefore, it is worth looking into the less popular, but immensely important, domain of quantum mechanics in non-inertial frames.

In this review, we will consider the quantum mechanical description of systems in non-inertial frames in detail. We will primarily examine the wave function, its evolution using the Schrodinger equation, and the physical observable. We will also investigate other intricacies brought on by the motion in non-inertial frames such as effective potentials and phase shifts in wave function.

The analysis is organised in 4 parts. In the first part (Chapter 4), we will look into the Galilean transformations and accelerated transformations, in the presence and absence of scalar or harmonic potentials. We will investigate the gauge transformation of the wave function that keeps the Schrodinger equation covariant for a particular coordinate transformation and we will report in details how the physical variables and effective potential changes in the transformed frame and the secondary effects they bring.

In the second part (Chapter 5), we will focus on three particularly important non-inertial

frames, namely; Extended Galilean frame, Co-moving frame, and Rotating frame. We will describe the system using classical mechanics and quantum mechanics, to explore the potential relationships connecting the two. Afterwards, we will focus on quantum Harmonic Oscillator systems and their usefulness in mapping them to different types of transformed systems. Using the coordinate transformation and gauge transformation of the wave function, we will solve some initial value problems there, which will also give us some insight into the effects of the transformation in the system under consideration.

In the third part (Chapter 6), we will study rotating frames in detail. We will analyse the system from relativistic and non-relativistic limits. We will investigate an equivalence between Galilean transformation and Lorentz transformation attained in non-relativistic limit. Even though the coordinate transformation and gauge transformation make the non-inertial frame covariant, there is a residual phase shift arising due to the coupling of rotation and spin, the effects of which we will investigate in detail.

In the last part (Chapter 7), we will consider the real-world applications of the studied non-inertial systems, particularly in Spintronics. We will go through the effect of phase shifts due to a non-inertial coupling that will assist in the generation and control of spin current, which otherwise is quite difficult to monitor and control. We will study other phase factors arising due to spin-orbit coupling and spin-rotation coupling. We will also explore various applications of non-inertial frames in Spintronics such as the spin galvanic effect, spin relaxation time, and spin filter. In essence, we will explore how the study of one subtle effect opens our view to an array of opportunities.

3. Problem Statement

Quantum mechanics in standard textbooks deals with inertial systems. However, systems need not always be inertial. Most practical systems are non-inertial, and to deal with them, we need a general quantum-mechanical description, the one that pertains to non-inertial systems as well. Our aim in this project is to find out the quantum-mechanical description of non-inertial systems, i.e., to find how the wave function, Schrodinger's equation, and other physical variables change in non-inertial frames and to investigate any additional phenomenons that may emerge in the non-inertial frames. And, most importantly, to find the potential real-world application of the same.

4. Inertial to Non Inertial Frames

We will consider the quantum description of selected systems in an inertial frame, S, and a non-inertial frame, S'. $\mathbf{x}, t, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{V}, \mathbf{a}, \psi, \phi, \mathbf{A}, \theta, \hat{H}, E, j, \rho,$ and w are respectively the position co-ordinate, time, momentum, velocity, acceleration, wave function, scalar potential, vector potential, phase factor, Hamiltonian, Energy, current density, charged density, and weight function in the S frame. Quantities denoted with a prime sign are the ones measured in the S' frame. Bold letters denote vector quantities and m is the mass of the particle.

4.1 Galilean Transformed Frame

As a first step, we consider a Galilean transformation from an inertial frame to a non-inertial frame. The coordinate transformations are below,

$$\mathbf{x}' = \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{V}t \quad (4.1)$$

$$t' = t \quad (4.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} + \mathbf{V} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \quad (4.3)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \quad (4.4)$$

The relation between corresponding momentum and accelerations is given as follows,

$$\mathbf{p}' = \mathbf{p} + m\mathbf{V} \quad (4.5)$$

$$\frac{d^2x}{dt^2} = 0 \quad (4.6)$$

$$\frac{d^2x'}{dt^2} = 0 \quad (4.7)$$

i.e., the classical description of both S and S' frames are equivalent.

Now, consider the quantum mechanical description of the system. Schrodinger equation in S frame is given by the equation,

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi(\mathbf{x}, t) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (4.8)$$

Using the coordinate transformation, we can examine the Schrodinger equation in S' frame.

$$i\hbar \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \psi(\mathbf{x}, t) + \mathbf{V} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{x}'} \psi(\mathbf{x}, t) \right) \right) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla'^2 \psi(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (4.9)$$

Let us consider the gauge transformation of the wave function given below.

$$\psi' = \psi \exp\left[\left(\frac{i}{\hbar}\right)(mV\mathbf{x}' - \frac{mV^2 t}{2})\right] \quad (4.10)$$

We use this gauge-transformed wave function (Equation 4.10) to substitute the wave function in the Schrodinger equation in S' frame (Equation 4.9). The result is as follows.

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \psi'(\mathbf{x}', t') = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla'^2 \psi'(\mathbf{x}', t') \quad (4.11)$$

i.e., the Schrodinger equation remains invariant in a non-inertial frame, given a gauge transformation is introduced.

Now, let us consider the wave function in detail.

The wave function in the S frame obtained after solving equation 4.8 is,

$$\psi = A \exp\left[\left(\frac{i}{\hbar}\right)(\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x} - Et)\right] \quad (4.12)$$

where A is the normalisation constant, and E is given by,

$$E = \frac{p^2}{2m} \quad (4.13)$$

From equation 4.10, we obtain the wave function in S' frame as,

$$\psi' = A \exp\left[\left(\frac{i}{\hbar}\right)[(\mathbf{p} + m\mathbf{V})\mathbf{x}' - (1/2m)\mathbf{p} + m\mathbf{V}^2 t]\right] \quad (4.14)$$

$$\psi' = A \exp[i(\mathbf{p}' \cdot \mathbf{x}' - E't')] \quad (4.15)$$

which is consistent with a solution in the S frame.

Let us check how the associated physical constants change as the system moves from an inertial to a non-inertial frame.

(1) Probability density

In the S frame,

$$\rho = |\psi|^2 \tag{4.16}$$

In the S' frame, from equation 4.10,

$$\rho' = \rho \tag{4.17}$$

i.e., probability density remains the same in inertial and non-inertial frames.

(2) Probability current

In s frame,

$$j = \frac{\hbar}{2m}(\psi^* \nabla \psi - \psi \nabla \psi^*) \tag{4.18}$$

In S' frame,

$$j' = j + \rho \mathbf{V} \tag{4.19}$$

i.e., probability current obeys the composition rule like momentum operator, as the frame transforms from inertial to non-inertial.

4.2 Uniformly Accelerated Frame

Let us consider an inertial frame, S, and a non-inertial frame, S', which is moving with a constant acceleration, \mathbf{a} , in the negative \mathbf{x} direction. The coordinate transformations are,

$$\mathbf{x}' = \mathbf{x} + \frac{\mathbf{a}t^2}{2} \tag{4.20}$$

$$t' = t \tag{4.21}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \tag{4.22}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} + \mathbf{a}t' \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \tag{4.23}$$

The equation of motion in classical mechanics is as follows.

$$\frac{\partial^2 x}{\partial t^2} - \mathbf{a} = 0 \quad (4.24)$$

which embodies the Principle of Equivalence.

The Schrodinger equation in the S frame is given as,

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi \quad (4.25)$$

After applying the coordinate transformation, we obtain the corresponding equation in S' frame as,

$$i\hbar \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \psi + \mathbf{a}t' \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \psi \right) \right) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla'^2 \psi \quad (4.26)$$

Let us define a suitable gauge transformation of the wave function for this particular frame transformation,

$$\psi' = \psi \exp\left[\left(\frac{i m \mathbf{a}}{\hbar}\right) \left(\mathbf{x}'t' - \frac{\mathbf{a}t'^3}{6}\right)\right] \quad (4.27)$$

Using the gauge transformed wave function (Equation 4.27), we obtain a covariant form of the Schrodinger equation in S' frame (Equation 4.26), as given below.

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \psi'(\mathbf{x}', t') = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla'^2 \psi'(\mathbf{x}', t') - m \mathbf{a} \mathbf{x}' \psi'(\mathbf{x}', t') \quad (4.28)$$

where momentum transformation is,

$$\mathbf{p}' = \mathbf{p} + m \mathbf{a} t \quad (4.29)$$

The momentum in S' frame includes an impulse which varies with time, unlike in Galilean transformation.

4.3 In the Presence of a Potential

Let us introduce a 1-D oscillator potential in our system under consideration. Let the source of the potential be in accelerated motion in the S frame, i.e., the source is considered to be at

the origin of the S' frame. Let the acceleration be in the positive \mathbf{x} direction. The coordinate transformations are,

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}' + \frac{\mathbf{a}t^2}{2} \quad (4.30)$$

$$\phi = \frac{mw^2x'^2}{2} \quad (4.31)$$

$$\phi = \frac{mw^2(\mathbf{x} - \frac{\mathbf{a}t^2}{2})^2}{2} \quad (4.32)$$

The equation of motion in classical mechanics is given as,

$$\frac{d^2\mathbf{x}'}{dt^2} = -w^2\mathbf{x}' \quad (4.33)$$

$$\frac{d^2\mathbf{x}}{dt^2} = \frac{d^2\mathbf{x}'}{dt^2} + \mathbf{a} \quad (4.34)$$

$$\frac{d^2\mathbf{x}}{dt^2} = -w^2(\mathbf{x} - \frac{\mathbf{a}t^2}{2}) + \mathbf{a} \quad (4.35)$$

Quantum mechanical description in S frame is,

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi + \frac{mw^2x'^2}{2} \psi \quad (4.36)$$

In S' frame, after applying coordinate transformations and gauge transformation of the wave function, as in section 4.2, we obtain,

$$i\hbar \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \psi' \right) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla'^2 \psi' + \left(\frac{mw^2x'^2}{2} - m\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x}' \right) \psi' \quad (4.37)$$

We are getting an additional term in the Schrodinger equation which acts as a potential. It is arising due to the acceleration of the frame. i.e., the Schrodinger equation remains invariant in a non-inertial frame with the introduction of an effective potential term that depends on the acceleration.

On rearranging terms, we obtain the following form.

$$i\hbar \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \psi' \right) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla'^2 \psi' + \left(\frac{mw^2(\mathbf{x}' - \frac{\mathbf{a}}{w^2})^2}{2} - \frac{ma^2}{2w^2} \right) \psi' \quad (4.38)$$

The effective potential has relocated the source of the oscillator potential to a new location,

$$\mathbf{x}' = \frac{\mathbf{a}}{w^2}$$

i.e., the origin has changed as a function of the acceleration.

Additionally, the effective potential has a constant term that changes the energy eigenvalues.

$$E_n = \hbar w \left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right) - \frac{ma^2}{2w^2} \quad (4.39)$$

Suppose there is more than one accelerating potential source, then the difference between the Schrodinger equation in S and S' frames is an effective potential, where the potential in accelerating frames will be decreased by an amount of $ma\mathbf{x}'\psi'$.

If Φ is the potential due to all the accelerating sources, then the quantum mechanical description takes the form,

$$i\hbar\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t'}\psi'\right) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\nabla'^2\psi' + (\Phi(\mathbf{x}') - ma\mathbf{x}')\psi' \quad (4.40)$$

Transformation of physical parameters is as follows,

$$\rho' = |A|^2 = \rho \quad (4.41)$$

$$j = \frac{\mathbf{P}\rho}{m} \quad (4.42)$$

$$j' = \frac{(\mathbf{P} + mat')\rho}{m} = j + \rho a t' \quad (4.43)$$

i.e., the physical observable remains the same

4.4 Solution of the Wave Equation

Let us go back to the wave function in the S frame. Generally, it can be written with a weight factor, as follows.

$$\psi = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} w(p) dp \exp[(i/\hbar)(\mathbf{p}' \cdot \mathbf{x}' - p^2 t/2m)] \quad (4.44)$$

The solution in the accelerated frame, using the Fourier transform, is given by,

$$\psi' = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} w'(k) dk Ai\left[\left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m^2 a}\right)^{1/3} \left(\mathbf{x}' + \frac{k}{ma}\right)\right] \exp\left[-\frac{ikt'}{\hbar}\right] \quad (4.45)$$

where $w(p)$ and $w'(k)$ are the weight functions, Ai is the airy function. Let us define another weight function,

$$\Omega(k) = \delta(k - K) \quad (4.46)$$

For airy function, we have the identity,

$$Ai[-(3c)^{1/3} \eta] = \frac{(3c)^{1/3}}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \exp[i(c\xi^3 - \eta\xi)] d\xi \quad (4.47)$$

Using the equations 4.41 and 4.45,

$$\psi = \frac{1}{2\pi} \left(\frac{1}{2m^2 a \hbar}\right)^{1/3} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \exp\left[\frac{i}{\hbar} \left(-\frac{p^3}{6m^2 a} + \frac{K\mathbf{p}}{ma} + \mathbf{x}\mathbf{p} - \frac{p^2 t}{2m}\right)\right] \quad (4.48)$$

where we have taken

$$\mathbf{p} = -\hbar\xi - mat \quad (4.49)$$

On comparing equation 4.44 with equation 4.48, we can identify the form of the weight function in frame S.

$$w(p) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \left(\frac{1}{2m^2 a \hbar}\right)^{1/3} \exp\left[\frac{i}{\hbar} \left(-\frac{p^3}{6m^2 a} + \frac{K\mathbf{p}}{ma}\right)\right] \quad (4.50)$$

On taking the Fourier transform,

$$w'(k) = \left(\frac{2}{ma^2 \hbar^2}\right)^{1/3} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \omega(p) dp \exp\left[\frac{i}{\hbar} \left(\frac{p^3}{6m^2 a} - \frac{k\mathbf{p}}{ma}\right)\right] \quad (4.51)$$

Now, let us choose a weight function in the S frame,

$$w(p) = \delta(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{P}) \quad (4.52)$$

Corresponding $\Omega(k)$ and ψ' are respectively,

$$\Omega(k) = \left(\frac{2}{ma^2\hbar^2}\right)^{1/3} A \exp\left[\frac{i}{\hbar}\left(\frac{\mathbf{P}^3}{6m^2a} - \frac{k\mathbf{P}}{ma}\right)\right] \quad (4.53)$$

$$\psi' = A \exp\left[\frac{i}{\hbar}\left(\frac{P^3 - (\mathbf{P} + mat')^3}{6m^2a} + x'(\mathbf{P} + mat')\right)\right] \quad (4.54)$$

The physical observables transform as follows,

$$\rho' = |A|^2 = \rho \quad (4.55)$$

$$\mathbf{j} = \frac{\mathbf{P}\rho}{m} \quad (4.56)$$

$$\mathbf{j}' = \frac{(\mathbf{P} + mat')\rho}{m} = \mathbf{j} + \rho\mathbf{a}t' \quad (4.57)$$

i.e., the probability current varies with time.

4.5 The Gauge Transformation

In this section, let us explore the method to find the phase factor for the gauge transformation of the wave function, for a particular frame transformation. Suppose we have a spinless particle of mass m in an inertial frame, S , in the presence of a constant potential, ϕ . Let S' be a frame moving with velocity \mathbf{V} along the positive \mathbf{x} axis. \mathbf{g} is the acceleration due to gravity. The coordinate transformations are,

$$\mathbf{x}' = \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{V}t \quad (4.58)$$

$$t' = t \quad (4.59)$$

$$\nabla' = \nabla \quad (4.60)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t'} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \mathbf{V} \cdot \nabla \quad (4.61)$$

$$\phi'(\mathbf{x}', t') = \phi(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (4.62)$$

The Schrodinger equation in the S frame becomes

$$i\hbar\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t}\psi\right) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\nabla^2\psi + \phi(\mathbf{x}, t)\psi \quad (4.63)$$

Let us define a general gauge transformation as,

$$\psi'(\vec{x}', t') = e^{i\theta} \psi(\vec{x}, t) \quad (4.64)$$

On applying the coordinate transformation and the gauge transformation, equation 4.63 becomes,

$$i\hbar\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t'} + \mathbf{V} \cdot \nabla'\right]e^{-i\theta}\psi' = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\nabla'^2 e^{-i\theta}\psi' + \phi' e^{-i\theta}\psi' \quad (4.65)$$

On expanding and equating the coefficients of ∇' , $\frac{\partial}{\partial t'}$ and ψ' , we get the following relations.

$$\theta = \frac{m}{\hbar}\left(\frac{V^2 t}{2} - \mathbf{V} \cdot \mathbf{x}\right) \quad (4.66)$$

$$i\hbar\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t'}\psi'\right) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\nabla'^2\psi' + \phi'(\mathbf{x}', t)\psi' \quad (4.67)$$

i.e., equation 4.66 gives the phase transformation to construct the gauge transformation of the wave function which helps to achieve the covariant form of the Schrodinger equation in S' .

Let us consider relativistic quantum mechanics to understand the significance of this phase factor. Consider the case,

$$\Psi'(\mathbf{x}', t') = \Psi(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (4.68)$$

$$E = mc^2 \quad (4.69)$$

$$\Psi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \exp\left[-\frac{mc^2 t}{\hbar}\right]\Psi_0(\mathbf{x}, 0) \quad (4.70)$$

$$\Psi(\mathbf{x}', t') = \exp\left[-\frac{mc^2(t' - t)}{\hbar}\right]\Psi_0(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (4.71)$$

$$t' = \frac{t - \frac{\mathbf{V} \cdot \mathbf{x}}{c^2}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \quad (4.72)$$

We can approximate to second order in $\frac{v}{c}$.

$$t' = \left(1 + \frac{v^2}{2c^2}\right)t - \frac{\mathbf{V} \cdot \mathbf{x}}{c^2} \quad (4.73)$$

$$\Psi(\mathbf{x}', t') = \exp\left[\frac{im}{\hbar}\left(\frac{\mathbf{V}^2 t}{2} - \mathbf{V} \cdot \mathbf{x}\right)\right] \Psi_0(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (4.74)$$

The phase factor is the same as what we obtained above (Equation 4.66). However, here Ψ is defined in the second-order relativistic theory.

For the low energy approximation, the Schrodinger equation in the S frame becomes,

$$i\hbar\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t}\Psi\right) = \left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\nabla^2 + \phi(\mathbf{x}, t) + mc^2\right]\Psi \quad (4.75)$$

4.6 The Equivalence Principle

In the classical description of a system, consider a gravitational field directed along the negative \mathbf{z} axis. The equation of motion is,

$$m_i \frac{d^2 z}{dt^2} = -m_g \mathbf{g} \quad (4.76)$$

Consider the reference frame S' which is accelerating in the negative \mathbf{z} direction. m_i and m_g are the inertial mass and gravitational mass of the particle. Coordinate transformations are,

$$\mathbf{z}' = \mathbf{z} + \frac{\mathbf{a}t^2}{2} \quad (4.77)$$

$$t' = t \quad (4.78)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z'} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \quad (4.79)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} + \mathbf{a}t \frac{\partial}{\partial z'} \quad (4.80)$$

$$\frac{d^2 z'}{dt^2} = \frac{d^2 z}{dt^2} + \mathbf{a} \quad (4.81)$$

$$\mathbf{a} = -|a|\hat{\mathbf{z}} \quad (4.82)$$

$$\frac{d^2 z'}{dt^2} = -\frac{m_g \mathbf{g}}{m_i} + \mathbf{a} \quad (4.83)$$

i.e., when $a = \frac{m_g g}{m_i}$ the particle acts as in free motion with respect to the accelerated frame, which is the essence of Einstein's Equivalence Principle. Also, the equality of m_i and m_g are verified to 2 in 10^{13} parts.

Let us consider the Schrodinger equation of the particle in the S frame for quantum mechanical treatment.

$$i\hbar\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t}\psi\right) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_i}\frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2}\psi + \phi(\mathbf{z})\psi \quad (4.84)$$

$$\phi(z) = m_g\mathbf{g}\mathbf{z} \quad (4.85)$$

On applying the coordinate transformation, equation 4.84 becomes,

$$i\hbar\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t'}\psi + \mathbf{a}t'\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial z'}\psi\right)\right) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\frac{\partial^2}{\partial z'^2}\psi + m_g\mathbf{g}\left(\mathbf{z}' - \frac{\mathbf{a}t'^2}{2}\right) \quad (4.86)$$

Let us define a gauge transformation,

$$\psi = e^{i\theta}\psi' \quad (4.87)$$

such that equation 4.86 reduces to the form,

$$i\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial t'}\psi' = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_i}\frac{\partial^2}{\partial z'^2}\psi' \quad (4.88)$$

In the remaining terms, on equating the coefficients of $\frac{\partial}{\partial z'}$, we get

$$-2i\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_i}\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial z'}\theta\right) = i\hbar\mathbf{a}t' \quad (4.89)$$

On integrating,

$$\theta = -\frac{m_i\mathbf{a}t'\mathbf{z}'}{\hbar} + f(t') \quad (4.90)$$

where $f(t')$ is an arbitrary function of time. Equating the coefficients of ϕ

$$-\hbar\mathbf{a}t'\frac{\partial}{\partial z'}\theta - \hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial z'}\theta = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_i}\left[m_g\mathbf{g}\left(\mathbf{z}' - \frac{\mathbf{a}t'^2}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial z'}\theta\right)^2 + i\frac{\partial^2\theta}{\partial z'^2}\right] \quad (4.91)$$

Substituting for the value of θ and solving for equation 4.91, we get,

$$\mathbf{a} = \frac{m_g \mathbf{g}}{m_i} \quad (4.92)$$

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial t'} = \frac{m_i a^2 t'^2}{\hbar} \quad (4.93)$$

equation 4.92 is the same as the condition we obtained in the classical treatment. Solving for equation 4.93 with initial condition $f(0) = 0$ yields the following results.

$$f(t') = \frac{m_i a^2 t'^3}{3\hbar} \quad (4.94)$$

$$\theta = -\frac{m_i \mathbf{a} t' \mathbf{z}'}{\hbar} + \frac{m_i a^2 t'^3}{3\hbar} \quad (4.95)$$

$$\psi(\mathbf{z}', t') = \psi'(\mathbf{z}', t') \exp\left[-\frac{i m_i \mathbf{a} t'}{\hbar} \left(\mathbf{z}' - \frac{\mathbf{a} t'^2}{3}\right)\right] \quad (4.96)$$

$$\psi(\mathbf{z}, t) = \psi'(\mathbf{z}, t) \exp\left[-\frac{i m_i \mathbf{a} t}{\hbar} \left(\mathbf{z} + \frac{\mathbf{a} t^2}{6}\right)\right] \quad (4.97)$$

The equality of m_i and m_g yields the equivalence of a and g which in turn gives the gravitational equivalence principle in quantum mechanics.

Putting the newly obtained ψ into the Schrodinger equation in S frame, we get

$$i\hbar \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t}\right) \psi' = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_i} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \psi' + \phi_{eff} \psi' \quad (4.98)$$

$$\phi_{eff} = \phi - m_i \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{z} + i\hbar \mathbf{a} t \nabla \quad (4.99)$$

Now, let us consider the scenario of a neutron interferometer that splits a neutron beam into two beams travelling the same distance d but at different heights. Using energy conservation, we can derive

$$\frac{p^2}{2m} = m_i \mathbf{g} \mathbf{z} \quad (4.100)$$

The momentum difference between the two neutron beams to first order in δp as,

$$\delta p = \frac{m_i^2 \mathbf{g} \mathbf{z}}{p} \quad (4.101)$$

From quantum mechanics,

$$p = \frac{2\pi\hbar}{\lambda} \quad (4.102)$$

Hence, the phase difference over a horizontal distance, d , is,

$$\Delta_c = \frac{d\delta p}{\hbar} \quad (4.103)$$

Substitute equations 4.102 and 4.101 in equation 4.103. We get the phase factor,

$$\Delta_c = \frac{m_i^2 \mathbf{g} \mathbf{z} \lambda d}{2\pi\hbar^2} \quad (4.104)$$

Suppose we take an interference of these two neutron beams.

$$t = \frac{d}{v} \quad (4.105)$$

$$v = \frac{2\pi\hbar}{m_i \lambda} \quad (4.106)$$

Substitute equations 4.105 and 4.106 in equation 4.103, and the phase factor calculated to the first order in d is,

$$\Delta = \frac{m_i^2 \mathbf{a} \mathbf{z} \lambda d}{2\pi\hbar^2} \quad (4.107)$$

With the aid of the equivalence principle, we find,

$$\Delta_c = \Delta \quad (4.108)$$

This phase shift causes interference and fringes are formed. Let us take a particular ψ' ,

$$\psi'(\mathbf{z}, t) = \exp\left[\frac{i}{\hbar}\left(p_0 \mathbf{z} - \frac{p_0^2 t}{2m_i}\right)\right] \quad (4.109)$$

$$\psi(\mathbf{z}, t) = \exp\left[\frac{i}{\hbar}\left(p_0 \mathbf{z} - \frac{p_0^2 t}{2m_i} - m_i \mathbf{a} t \left(\mathbf{z} + \frac{\mathbf{a} t^2}{6}\right)\right)\right] \quad (4.110)$$

$$-i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial z} = \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{t})\psi \quad (4.111)$$

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = \left[-\frac{p(t)^2}{2m_i} + \frac{am_i \mathbf{z}}{2} \right] \psi \quad (4.112)$$

$$\mathbf{p}(t) = \mathbf{p}_0 - m_i \mathbf{a} t \quad (4.113)$$

Which is the same as the result obtained using the classical mechanical description of the system. Neutron interference discussed here verifies the validity of the Schrodinger equation for particles in gravitational fields.

5. More on Non-Inertial Frames

Consider a charged particle of charge q and mass m in an external electromagnetic field described by a vector potential \mathbf{A} and in an external force field ϕ . The Schrodinger equation in the S frame is,

$$i\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial t} = \left(-\frac{1}{2}[\nabla - i\mathbf{A}]^2 + \phi\right)\psi \quad (5.1)$$

5.1 Non-Inertial Frames

Let us examine the equation of motion of this charged particle (equation 5.1) in three non-inertial systems with definite coordinate transformations;

(a) Extended Galilean Frame

The frame S' moves with a time-dependent velocity, $R(t)$, w.r.t S .

$$\mathbf{x}' = \mathbf{x} - R(t) \quad (5.2)$$

$$t' = t \quad (5.3)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} - \dot{R} \cdot \nabla' \quad (5.4)$$

$$\nabla = \nabla' \quad (5.5)$$

These coordinate transformations are useful for a system with potentials that are of the form,

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) = \phi(\mathbf{x} - R(t)) \quad (5.6)$$

The gauge transformation of the wave function selected for such coordinate transformation is,

$$\psi' = \exp[-i\dot{R}\cdot\mathbf{x}' - i\int_{t_0}^t dt' \frac{\dot{R}^2}{2}] \psi \quad (5.7)$$

Using equations 5.2, 5.3, and 5.7 on equation 5.1, the Schrodinger equation in the transformed frame becomes,

$$i\frac{\partial\psi'}{\partial t'} = [-\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{D}^2 + \Phi]\psi' \quad (5.8)$$

where,

$$\mathbf{D} = \nabla - i\mathbf{A} \quad (5.9)$$

$$\Phi = \phi - \dot{R}\cdot\mathbf{A} + \ddot{R} \quad (5.10)$$

The last term in equation 5.10 corresponds to a fictitious force. The second term is the electric scalar potential induced by the frame's motion.

(b) Comoving Frame

Comoving frames expand with the system and effectively nullify the need to bring the complexities of expansion into the analysis. They are particularly useful in the study of the context of the expanding universe.

$$\mathbf{x}' = \frac{\mathbf{x}}{b(t)} \quad (5.11)$$

$$t' = t \quad (5.12)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} - \frac{\dot{b}x}{b}\cdot\nabla' \quad (5.13)$$

$$\nabla = \frac{\nabla'}{b} \quad (5.14)$$

It is useful in the presence of a potential of the form,

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{\phi(\mathbf{x}')}{b^2} \quad (5.15)$$

$$\psi = b^{\frac{d}{2}} \exp\left(\frac{-ib\dot{b}\mathbf{x}'^2}{2}\right)\psi' \quad (5.16)$$

Using equations 5.11 and 5.12 on equation 5.1, we get

$$i\frac{\partial\psi'}{\partial t'} = [-\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{D}^2 + \Phi]\psi' \quad (5.17)$$

where,

$$\mathbf{D} = \nabla - ib\mathbf{A} \quad (5.18)$$

$$\Phi = [\phi - \dot{b}\mathbf{x}' \cdot \mathbf{A} + \frac{1}{2}b\ddot{b}\mathbf{x}'^2]b^2 \quad (5.19)$$

(c) Rotating Frame

S' is a rotating frame w.r.t. S frame with time-dependent angular velocity. We perform the rotation in 3D. Corresponding ortho-normal right-handed triad are $[\mathbf{e}_j | j = 1, 2, 3]$.

$$\dot{\mathbf{e}}_j = \vec{\Omega} \times \mathbf{e}_j \quad (5.20)$$

$$\mathbf{e}_j(t_0) = \mathbf{e}_j \quad (5.21)$$

$$x'_j = x_j \cdot \mathbf{e}_j(t) \quad (5.22)$$

$$t' = t \quad (5.23)$$

$$\nabla = \mathbf{e}_j \cdot \nabla'_j \quad (5.24)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} - i\vec{\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{L} \quad (5.25)$$

We choose a cylindrical symmetry for the rotation,

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}, t) \times \mathbf{x} \quad (5.26)$$

We get the Hamiltonian as,

$$H = -\frac{1}{2}\nabla^2 - \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{L} + \phi + \frac{1}{8}(\mathbf{B} \times \mathbf{x}^2) \quad (5.27)$$

and, equation 5.1 becomes,

$$i\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial t'} = [-\frac{1}{2}\nabla^2 + \Phi - \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{B} + \vec{\Omega}) \cdot \mathbf{L}]\psi \quad (5.28)$$

$$\Phi = \phi + \frac{1}{8}(\mathbf{B} \times \mathbf{x}') \quad (5.29)$$

5.2 Classical Analysis

In this section, let us use action integral, I , instead of Schrodinger equation to describe the system.

$$I = \int L dt \quad (5.30)$$

L is the Lagrangian of a charged particle of mass 'm' and charge 'q' in an external electromagnetic field. For the Extended Galilean Frame, equation 5.31 becomes,

$$L = \frac{1}{2}\dot{\mathbf{x}}'^2 + \dot{\mathbf{x}}' \cdot \dot{R} + \dot{\mathbf{x}}' \cdot \mathbf{A} + \dot{R} \cdot \mathbf{A} - \phi + \frac{1}{2}\dot{R}^2 \quad (5.31)$$

We can find I to be in the form,

$$I = \theta + \int dt L_{EGF} \quad (5.32)$$

$$L_{EGF} = \frac{1}{2}\dot{\mathbf{x}}'^2 + \dot{\mathbf{x}}' \cdot \mathbf{A} - \Phi \quad (5.33)$$

$$\Phi = \phi - \dot{R} \cdot \mathbf{A} - \ddot{R} \cdot \mathbf{x}' \quad (5.34)$$

$$\theta = \dot{R} \cdot \mathbf{x}' \quad (5.35)$$

here, θ is the same as the phase factor we used for the gauge transformation of the wave function in quantum mechanical analysis.

$$\mathbf{p}_{EGF} = \dot{\mathbf{x}}' + \mathbf{A} \quad (5.36)$$

$$H_{EGF} = \frac{1}{2}[\mathbf{p}_{EGF} - \mathbf{A}]^2 + \Phi \quad (5.37)$$

In Comoving Frame, equation 5.31 becomes,

$$L = \frac{1}{2}b^2\dot{\mathbf{x}}'^2 + \dot{\mathbf{x}}' \cdot \mathbf{x}' b \dot{b} + b \dot{\mathbf{x}}' \cdot \mathbf{A} + \dot{b} \mathbf{x}' \cdot \mathbf{A} - \phi + \frac{1}{2}\dot{b}^2 x'^2 \quad (5.38)$$

We find the form of I to be,

$$I = \theta + \int dt L_{CF} \quad (5.39)$$

$$L_{CF} = \frac{1}{2}b^2\dot{\mathbf{x}}' + b\dot{\mathbf{x}}'.\mathbf{A} - \Phi \quad (5.40)$$

$$\Phi = \phi - b\dot{\mathbf{x}}'.\mathbf{A} + \frac{1}{2}b\ddot{\mathbf{x}}'.\mathbf{x}'^2 \quad (5.41)$$

$$\theta = b\dot{\mathbf{x}}'.\mathbf{x}'^2 \quad (5.42)$$

Again, θ is the same as the phase factor we used for the gauge transformation of the wave function in the quantum mechanical analysis.

$$\mathbf{p}_{CF} = b\dot{\mathbf{x}}' + b\mathbf{A} \quad (5.43)$$

$$H_{CF} = \frac{1}{2}[\mathbf{p}_{CF} - B\mathbf{A}]^2 + \Phi \quad (5.44)$$

In the Rotating Frame, equation 5.31 becomes,

$$L = \frac{1}{2}\dot{\mathbf{x}}'^2 + \left(\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{B} + \vec{\Omega}\right).(\mathbf{x}' \times \dot{\mathbf{x}}') + \frac{1}{2}[(\mathbf{B} + \vec{\Omega}) \times \mathbf{x}'] . (\vec{\Omega} \times \mathbf{x}') - \phi \quad (5.45)$$

$$L_{RF} = L \quad (5.46)$$

$$\theta = 0 \quad (5.47)$$

Again, θ is the same as the phase factor we used for the gauge transformation of the wave function in the quantum mechanical analysis.

$$\mathbf{p}_{RF} = \dot{\mathbf{x}}' + \left(\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{B} + \vec{\Omega}\right) \times \mathbf{x}' \quad (5.48)$$

$$H_{RF} = \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{p}_{RF}^2 - \left(\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{B} + \vec{\Omega}\right).(\mathbf{x}' \times \mathbf{p}_{RF}) + \Phi \quad (5.49)$$

$$\Phi = \phi + \frac{1}{8}(\mathbf{B} \times \mathbf{x}')^2 \quad (5.50)$$

Here, we can use the classical equation of motion from geometrical analysis, namely, Cartan's Geometrical Perspective. The classical equation of motion of a charged particle of mass $m = 1$ and charge $q = 1$ in an external electromagnetic field is given by,

$$\ddot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{E} + \dot{\mathbf{x}} \times \mathbf{B} \quad (5.51)$$

$$\mathbf{E} = -\nabla\phi - \frac{\partial\mathbf{A}}{\partial t} \quad (5.52)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A} \quad (5.53)$$

The geodesic equation of motion is,

$$\frac{\partial^2 x^{\hat{\alpha}}}{\partial \sigma^2} + \Gamma_{\hat{\beta}\hat{\gamma}}^{\hat{\alpha}} \left(\frac{\partial x^{\hat{\beta}}}{\partial \sigma} \right) \left(\frac{\partial x^{\hat{\gamma}}}{\partial \sigma} \right) = 0 \quad (5.54)$$

Using electromagnetic tensor and by comparing equations 5.52 and 5.55,

$$\Gamma_{\hat{0}\hat{0}}^{\hat{j}} = -E_j \quad (5.55)$$

$$\Gamma_{\hat{0}\hat{k}}^{\hat{j}} = -\epsilon_{jkl} \mathbf{B}_l \quad (5.56)$$

We can use this method to analyze the above-mentioned systems [4].

5.3 The Harmonic Oscillator Problem

For an isotropic harmonic oscillator,

$$i \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = \left[-\frac{\nabla^2}{2} + \frac{\omega^2 \mathbf{x}^2}{2} \right] \psi \quad (5.57)$$

In a co-moving frame,

$$i \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = \left[-\frac{1}{2} \nabla^2 + \frac{1}{2} b^3 (\ddot{b} + w^2 b) x^2 \right] \psi \quad (5.58)$$

consider the choice,

$$\ddot{b} + w^2 b = \frac{v^2}{b^2} \quad (5.59)$$

where v is an arbitrary function of time.

We are assuming the frame is oscillating like a harmonic oscillator with an angular frequency of v .

(1) HO-FP Equivalence

When $v = 0$, the coordinate system oscillates with the same frequency as that of the harmonic oscillator (HO) under study. Hence, in the transformed frame, the system appears like a free particle (FP).

Example: Consider a HO prepared in the n th excited state.

$$\psi(\mathbf{x}, 0) = H_n(\mathbf{x}) \exp\left[-\frac{x^2}{2}\right] \quad (5.60)$$

It is made to evolve as an FP by switching off the Harmonic potential. Time evolution is found by convoluting it with the Feynman kernel for a free particle.

$$\psi(\mathbf{x}', t) = \sqrt{2\pi i\tau} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dy \psi(\mathbf{y}', 0) \exp\left[i\frac{(\mathbf{y}' - \mathbf{x}')^2}{2\tau}\right] \quad (5.61)$$

Since the direct integral is tedious, we choose a scale factor,

$$b = \cos t \quad (5.62)$$

$$\tau = \tan t \quad (5.63)$$

Time evolved HO solution for a harmonic oscillator of unit angular frequency is,

$$\psi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \psi(\mathbf{x}, 0) \exp\left[-i\hbar\left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right)t\right] \quad (5.64)$$

By using equations 5.16 and 5.17,

$$\psi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi i\tau} |\delta|} \left(\frac{\delta^*}{\delta}\right)^{\frac{n}{2}} H_n\left(\frac{x}{|\delta|}\right) \exp\left[-\frac{x'^2 b}{2\delta}\right] \quad (5.65)$$

where,

$$\delta = 1 + i\tau \quad (5.66)$$

$$|\delta| = \frac{1}{b} \quad (5.67)$$

(2) HO-HO Equivalence

When $v \neq 0$, the coordinate system oscillates with a different frequency than that of the harmonic oscillator under study. Hence, in the transformed frame, the system appears like a harmonic oscillator of a different frequency.

Example: Squeezed State

The initial state is a Gaussian wave packet whose width differs from that of the ground state is given by the equation,

$$\psi(\mathbf{x}, 0) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\Delta_0}} \exp\left[-\frac{\mathbf{x}^2}{2\Delta_0^2}\right] \quad (5.68)$$

$$\psi(\mathbf{x}', t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dp A_p \exp\left[i\left(p\mathbf{x}' - \frac{p^2\tau}{2m}\right)\right] \quad (5.69)$$

$$\psi(\mathbf{x}', 0) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dp A_p \exp\left[i\frac{p\mathbf{x}'}{2m}\right] \quad (5.70)$$

We can find,

$$A_p = \sqrt{\frac{\Delta_0}{2\pi}} \exp\left[-\frac{\Delta_0^2 p_0^2}{2}\right] \quad (5.71)$$

$$\psi(\mathbf{x}', t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\delta}} \exp\left[-\frac{\mathbf{x}'^2}{2\Delta_0^2\delta}\right] \quad (5.72)$$

where,

$$\delta = \frac{\delta_0^2 + i\tau}{\Delta_0} \quad (5.73)$$

Using equation 5.16, we obtain

$$\psi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\Delta}} \exp\left[-\frac{x^2}{2\lambda^2 b}\right] \quad (5.74)$$

where,

$$\Delta = \delta b \quad (5.75)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\Delta_0\Delta} - i\dot{b}}} \quad (5.76)$$

$$\delta = \Delta + \frac{i\tau}{\Delta_0} \quad (5.77)$$

$$\Delta = \Delta_0 + \frac{i}{0} \quad (5.78)$$

(3) FP-FP Equivalence

When $v = 0$ and $\omega = 0$, i.e., when the motion in the transformed frame is like that of a free particle,

$$\psi(\mathbf{x}, o) = \exp\left[-\frac{x^2}{2\lambda^2}\right] \quad (5.79)$$

$$\psi(\mathbf{x}', \tau) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\delta}} \exp\left[-\frac{x'^2}{2\delta}\right] \quad (5.80)$$

where,

$$\tau = \frac{t}{b} \quad (5.81)$$

$$\lambda = \sqrt{\frac{b}{\frac{1}{\Delta} - i\dot{b}}} \quad (5.82)$$

$$\psi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \exp\left[-\frac{ux^2}{2}\right] \quad (5.83)$$

where,

$$u = 1 - i\dot{b} \quad (5.84)$$

To solve the initial value problem in one frame, inertial or non-inertial, we can use the transformed frame and the equivalence discussed above.

Similarly, we can solve more initial value problems using this relation [5].

6. Into Rotating Frames

Rotating frames are a common non-inertial frame met in different physical systems. The rotated frames are generally dealt with in quantum mechanics using position-dependent boosts, i.e., a composition of a rotation and boost, that connects them to non-rotational frames. The macroscopic properties of the system are not affected by the uniform rotation, except the centrifugal and Coriolis forces. But, there are residual phase shifts, arising due to the rotation in a quantum system.

B , Ω , and Φ respectively denote the magnetic field, angular velocity, and enclosed flux in the S frame. We will take $\hbar = 1$ and $c = 1$ for the analyses in this section [7].

6.1 Lorentz and Galilean Transformations in Quantum Mechanics

Consider a spinless particle. Let the associated scalar field $\psi(x^\mu)$ transform under the infinitesimal Lorentz boost,

$$\Lambda_\nu^\mu = I_\nu^\mu + \omega_\nu^\mu \quad (6.1)$$

$$\delta\Psi(x^\mu) = \Psi(x^{\mu'}) - \Psi(x^\mu) \quad (6.2)$$

$$x^{\mu'} = \Lambda_\nu^\mu x^\nu \quad (6.3)$$

On rearranging equation 6.2 using contraction,

$$\delta\Psi(x^\mu) = \frac{i}{2}\omega_{\mu\nu}L^{\mu\nu}\Psi(x^\mu) \quad (6.4)$$

where $L^{\mu\nu}$ are the generators of the Lagrangian given by

$$L^{\mu\nu} = x^\mu p^\nu - x^\nu p^\mu \quad (6.5)$$

$$\Psi(x'_\mu) = \Psi(x^\mu) + \frac{i}{2}\omega_{\mu\nu}L^{\mu\nu}\Psi(x^\mu) \quad (6.6)$$

$$\Psi(x'_\mu) = U\Psi(x^\mu) \quad (6.7)$$

The infinitesimal Lorentz transformation along x^i direction, using contraction, is,

$$U = I + i\omega_{0i}L^{0i} \quad (6.8)$$

We can make infinitesimal transformation a finite transformation by using the identity

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(1 + \frac{x}{n}\right)^n = e^x \quad (6.9)$$

i.e.,

$$U = \exp[i\omega_{0i}(x^0 p^i - x^i p^0)] \quad (6.10)$$

In the non-relativistic limit,

$$U = \exp[i(t\mathbf{V}\cdot\mathbf{p} - m\mathbf{V}\cdot\mathbf{x})] \quad (6.11)$$

This is similar to the phase factor in equation 6.10, i.e., in the non-relativistic limit, the Lorentz boost coincides with the Galilean boost. We can deal with the system in two equivalent ways, using the Galilean boost.

Consider a Galilean boosted frame moving w.r.t. to S frame, with a velocity V along the positive \mathbf{x} axis.

$$\mathbf{x}' = \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{V}t \quad (6.12)$$

$$t' = t \quad (6.13)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} - \mathbf{V} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \quad (6.14)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \quad (6.15)$$

(i) **Schrodinger Picture**

$$\Psi'(\mathbf{x}', t') = \exp\left[i\left(\frac{mV^2 t}{2} - m\mathbf{V}\cdot\mathbf{x}\right)\right]\Psi(x, t) \quad (6.16)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}}' = \hat{\mathbf{p}} \quad (6.17)$$

(ii) **Heisenberg Picture**

$$\Psi'(\mathbf{x}', t') = \Psi(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (6.18)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}}' = \exp[-i(\frac{mV^2t}{2} - m\mathbf{V}\cdot\mathbf{x})]\hat{\mathbf{p}}\exp[i(\frac{mV^2t}{2} - m\mathbf{V}\cdot\mathbf{x})] \quad (6.19)$$

we can simplify this expression using Baker-Campbell Relation,

$$e^{\hat{A}}\hat{B}e^{-\hat{A}} = \hat{B} + [\hat{A}, \hat{B}] + \frac{1}{2!}[\hat{A}, [\hat{A}, \hat{B}]] + \frac{1}{3!}[\hat{A}, [\hat{A}, [\hat{A}, \hat{B}]]] + \dots \quad (6.20)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}}' = \hat{\mathbf{p}} - m\mathbf{V} \quad (6.21)$$

Consider the function

$$e^{if(x,t)} = \exp[i(\frac{mV^2t}{2} - m\mathbf{V}\cdot\mathbf{x})] \quad (6.22)$$

Returning to the above-mentioned frames, we can see,

(i) **Schrodinger Picture**

$$\Psi' = e^{if(x,t)}\Psi \quad (6.23)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}}' = \hat{\mathbf{p}} \quad (6.24)$$

(ii) **Heisenberg Picture**

$$\Psi'(\mathbf{x}', t') = \Psi(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (6.25)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}}' = e^{-if(x,t)}\hat{\mathbf{p}}e^{if(x,t)} \quad (6.26)$$

Both Pictures yield the same expectation values. Equation 6.18 serves as a gauge transformation between these two pictures, and it is the same gauge transformation as in equation 4.10. We can adjust the phase factor and formulate infinitely many of them to do the gauge transformation for the same system without disturbing the physical observable.

Let us consider,

$$\Psi = e^{(ikx)} \quad (6.27)$$

Using equation 6.12 in Schrodinger's picture, we get,

$$\Psi' = \Psi'(\mathbf{x}', t') = \exp[i(\frac{mV^2t}{2} - m\mathbf{V}\cdot\mathbf{x} + kx)] \quad (6.28)$$

and in Heisenberg's picture,

$$\Psi' = e^{ikx} \quad (6.29)$$

If we consider the λ corresponding to k , it remains the same in the Heisenberg picture. However, it is reduced in the Schrodinger picture. At the same time, $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$ remains the same in the Schrodinger picture and reduces in the Heisenberg picture. This is consistent with the de Broglie relation.

Consider Schrodinger's equation of a particle in S' frame. Using the Heisenberg picture, we have

$$i\frac{\partial\Psi}{\partial t} = H\Psi \quad (6.30)$$

Transforming to S' frame

$$\hat{H} = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{p}}^2}{2m} \quad (6.31)$$

On applying the coordinate transformation,

$$i\left(\frac{\partial\Psi}{\partial t'} - V\cdot\nabla'\Psi\right) = \hat{H}'(\mathbf{x}, t)\Psi \quad (6.32)$$

$$\hat{H}' = e^{-if(x,t)}\hat{H}e^{if(x,t)} \quad (6.33)$$

$$H'\Psi' = E'\Psi' \quad (6.34)$$

using equations 8.20, 8.21, 8.22, and 8.31, we obtain,

$$\hat{H}' = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{p}}'^2}{2m} \quad (6.35)$$

$$\hat{E}' = i\frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \quad (6.36)$$

$$\hat{E}' = i\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t'} + \mathbf{V}\cdot\nabla'\right] \quad (6.37)$$

$$\hat{E}' = \hat{E} - \mathbf{V}\cdot\mathbf{p} \quad (6.38)$$

Let us try another way. The Lorentz transformation for energy is,

$$E' = \frac{E - \mathbf{V} \cdot \mathbf{p}}{\sqrt{1 - V^2}} \quad (6.39)$$

In the relativistic limit,

$$E' = E - \mathbf{V} \cdot \mathbf{p} + \frac{mV^2}{2} \quad (6.40)$$

$$E' = \frac{p'^2}{2m} \quad (6.41)$$

which is in agreement with equation 6.35. i.e., the energy measured in the Galilean transformed frame can be obtained from the non-relativistic limit of Lorentz transformation.

On rearranging equation 6.32,

$$i\left(\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t'} + \frac{mV^2}{2}\Psi\right) = \frac{(\mathbf{p}' - m\mathbf{V})^2}{2m}\Psi \quad (6.42)$$

This result is equivalent to the minimal coupling by a coupling constant m with a gauge field given by the relation,

$$A^\mu = \left(-\frac{mV^2}{2}, \mathbf{V}\right) \quad (6.43)$$

6.2 Non Relativistic Aspects of the Rotating Frame

Consider a uniformly rotating frame S'' , which rotates with an angular velocity $-\Omega$ w.r.t. S frame which is at rest. Consider a spinless particle at rest in S'' .

Let us define,

$$\mathbf{V} = \Omega \times \mathbf{x} \quad (6.44)$$

from equation 6.11, we obtain

$$U = \exp[it(\mathbf{L} \cdot \Omega)] \quad (6.45)$$

where L is the angular momentum of the particle. The boost U transforms the S frame to the S' frame, instead of the S'' frame. A boost from S to S'' depends on the position and therefore

can not be expressed as a single transformation. The transformation from S to S' should be aided by two Lorentz transformations, or a Lorentz transformation and a rotation. Or else we can take the non-relativistic limit of minimal coupling gauge fields.

The gauge field A^μ is given by

$$A^\mu(x^\mu) = (A_0(\mathbf{x}), \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x})) \quad (6.46)$$

$$A^\mu(x^\mu) = \left(\frac{(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{x})^2}{2}, (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{x}) \right) \quad (6.47)$$

We know that the Hamiltonian of a charged particle of charge q in an external electromagnetic field (ϕ, A) is given by the relation,

$$H = \frac{(\mathbf{p} - q\mathbf{A})^2}{2m} + q\phi \quad (6.48)$$

for which the minimal coupling gauge field is (ϕ, A) and the coupling constant is q . By analogy, the Hamiltonian of a particle at rest w.r.t. the rotating frame, S'', is,

$$\hat{H} = \frac{(\mathbf{p} - m(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{x}))^2}{2m} - \frac{m(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{x})^2}{2} \quad (6.49)$$

On simplifying,

$$\hat{H} = \frac{p^2}{2m} - \frac{\hat{\mathbf{p}} \cdot (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{x})}{2} - \frac{((\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{x}) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{p}})}{2} \quad (6.50)$$

We want to know the equation of motion of \mathbf{x} . On deriving,

$$\frac{\partial x_i}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{i\hbar} [x_i, \hat{H}] \quad (6.51)$$

$$\frac{\partial \langle \mathbf{x} \rangle}{\partial t} = \left\langle \left(\frac{\hat{p}}{m} - (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{x}) \right) \right\rangle \quad (6.52)$$

Repeating the calculation for $m \frac{\partial^2 \langle \mathbf{x} \rangle}{\partial t^2}$ using equation 6.51 and substituting equation 6.52, we obtain,

$$m \frac{\partial^2 \langle \mathbf{x} \rangle}{\partial t^2} = 2m \left(\frac{\partial \langle \mathbf{x} \rangle}{\partial t} \right) \times \boldsymbol{\Omega} + m\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times (\langle \mathbf{x} \rangle \times \boldsymbol{\Omega}) \quad (6.53)$$

where the first term in the RHS can be identified with Coriolis force and the second term with centrifugal force.

Consider a particle with spin, for example, a neutron with spin $\frac{1}{2}$. It is rotating with an angular velocity $-\Omega$ w.r.t. S frame. There is an interaction between spin and rotation which is the same as the Thomas Precession. Hence, equation 6.49 modifies as,

$$\hat{H} = \frac{(\mathbf{p} - m(\Omega \times \mathbf{x}))^2}{2m} - \frac{m(\Omega \times \mathbf{x})^2}{2} - \Omega \cdot \hat{S} \quad (6.54)$$

Where \hat{S} is the spin operator of the particle. We can derive the phase shift corresponding to Thomas's precession from equation 6.54.

In the rotating frame, the effect of rotation can be simulated by the Coriolis force. This fictitious velocity-dependent force is analogous to the Lorentz force on a charged particle of charge q in an external E.M. field.

$$\mathbf{F}_{Lor} = q\mathbf{V} \times \mathbf{B} \quad (6.55)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{cor} = 2m(\mathbf{V} \times \mathbf{B}) \quad (6.56)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A} \quad (6.57)$$

The canonical momentum in a rotating frame is,

$$\mathbf{p} = m\mathbf{V} + m(\Omega \times \mathbf{x}) \quad (6.58)$$

The canonical momentum of a charged particle in an external electromagnetic field is,

$$\mathbf{p} = m\mathbf{V} + q\mathbf{A} \quad (6.59)$$

i.e.,

$$q\mathbf{B} \rightarrow 2m\omega \quad (6.60)$$

Let us choose the form of \mathbf{A} to be,

$$\mathbf{A} = \frac{\mathbf{B} \times \mathbf{x}}{2} \quad (6.61)$$

The Aharonov-Bohm (AB) phase shift is given by,

$$\Delta\theta = \frac{q}{\hbar}\Phi \quad (6.62)$$

where Φ is the flux enclosed.

In analogy to the calculation of the Aharonov-Bohm effect, when a beam of charged particles in the presence of A is split into 2 alternate paths and recombined after travelling equal distances, then there is a phase difference in phase of these two beams which is proportional to the magnitude of flux enclosed by the paths.

$$\Delta\theta = q \oint_l A \cdot d\vec{l} \quad (6.63)$$

Using Stokes theorem and equation 6.61, we obtain

$$\Delta\theta = q \int_s B \cdot d\vec{s} \quad (6.64)$$

using equation 8.60

$$\Delta\theta = \frac{2m}{\hbar} \int_s \Omega \cdot d\vec{s} \quad (6.65)$$

$$\Delta\theta_{sagnac} = \frac{2m}{\hbar} s \cdot \Omega \quad (6.66)$$

where s is the area enclosed by the path of the neutron beam.

The effect of rotation coupling with spin can be expressed as an operator $\hat{\Phi}_{spin}$, which acts on the initial wave function and brings out the rotation-spin coupling-induced phase change.

Referring to equations 6.54 and 6.66, we obtain

$$\hat{\Phi}_{spin} = \hat{T} \exp\left[\frac{i}{\hbar} \int dt' \Omega \cdot \hat{S}\right] \quad (6.67)$$

where \hat{T} is the time ordering operator.

$$\hat{S} = \frac{\hbar \hat{\sigma}}{2} \quad (6.68)$$

Where $\hat{\sigma} = (\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z)$ are the Pauli's spin matrices.

Euler's identity for a matrix \hat{X} and a scalar θ is given by,

$$\exp[i\hat{X}\theta] = \hat{I} \cos(\theta) + \hat{X} \sin(\theta) \quad (6.69)$$

Using equations 6.68, 6.67, and 7.69, we obtain,

$$\hat{\Phi}_{spin} = \hat{I} \cos\left(\frac{\Omega t}{2}\right) + i \frac{\hat{\sigma} \cdot \Omega}{|\Omega|} \sin\left(\frac{\Omega t}{2}\right) \quad (6.70)$$

6.3 Relativistic Aspects of the Rotating Frame

In this section, we will discuss the relativistic aspects of rotating frames in quantum mechanics using the Dirac equation with spin connection, defined as,

$$(i\gamma^\mu \nabla_\mu - m)\psi = 0 \quad (6.71)$$

Where ∇_μ is defined as,

$$\nabla_\mu = \partial_\mu - \frac{i}{4} \Gamma_\mu^{ab} M_{ab} \quad (6.72)$$

$$M^{ab} = \frac{i}{2} [\gamma^a, \gamma^b] \quad (6.73)$$

where, Γ_μ^{ab} are Christoffel symbols and γ^μ are Dirac matrices. The Latin indices with μ, ν , and a, b runs from 0 to 3. The Greek indices; i, j, k run from 1 to 3. The commutator of γ^μ can be calculated to be,

$$[\gamma^0, \gamma^i] = 2\alpha^i \quad (6.74)$$

$$\alpha^i = \gamma^0 \gamma^i \quad (6.75)$$

$$[\gamma^i, \gamma^j] = 2\gamma^i \gamma^j \quad (6.76)$$

The components, $g_{\mu\nu}$, of the metric tensor in a uniformly rotating frame are given by,

$$g_{00} = 1 - (\Omega \times \mathbf{x})^2 \quad (6.77)$$

$$g_{ii} = -1 \quad (6.78)$$

$$g_{0,i} = -(\Omega \times \mathbf{x})^i \quad (6.79)$$

otherwise, $g_{\mu\nu} = 0$.

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \eta_{\mu\nu} + h_{\mu\nu} \quad (6.80)$$

where, $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor for flat space.

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \eta_{ab} e_\mu^a e_\nu^b \quad (6.81)$$

where e_μ^a constitutes the Vierbein. In the low energy limit, up to the order of $(\frac{v}{c})^2$,

$$\Gamma_{ab\mu} = \frac{1}{2}(\partial_a h_{\mu b} - \partial_b h_{\mu a}) = -\Gamma_{ba\mu} \quad (6.82)$$

We rewrite the spinor as

$$\psi \rightarrow e^{-imt} \psi \quad (6.83)$$

We can obtain the low energy limit of the Dirac equation (equation 6.72) using equation 6.83 as,

$$[\gamma^0(m + \hat{p}_0 - mA_0 - \frac{A^i \hat{p}_i}{2}) + \gamma^i(\hat{p}_i = \frac{mA_i}{2} - \frac{i\vec{\epsilon}_i}{2})]\psi = 0 \quad (6.84)$$

where,

$$\vec{\epsilon} = -\frac{\nabla h_{00}}{2} \quad (6.85)$$

$$\vec{\epsilon} = -\nabla A_0 \quad (6.86)$$

$$H = \frac{1}{2m}(\hat{\mathbf{p}} - m\mathbf{A} - \hat{\mathbf{S}} \times \vec{\epsilon})^2 + mA_0 - \Omega \cdot \hat{\mathbf{S}} - \frac{\nabla \cdot \vec{\epsilon}}{8m} \quad (6.87)$$

The last term in equation 6.87 is analogous to the Darwin term, $-\frac{3\Omega^2}{8mc^2}$. In the rotating frame,

$$\vec{\epsilon} = \frac{\Omega^2 \mathbf{x}}{c^2} \quad (6.88)$$

i.e., we can neglect the $\hat{\mathbf{S}} \times \epsilon$ term in equation 6.87 which is of the order c^{-2} . Then, equations 6.87 and 6.54 become identical. We can get the phase shift the same way we obtained equation 6.66. However, there is an additional phase shift here.

$$\hat{\Phi}_r = P[\exp(\frac{i}{\hbar} \oint \vec{dl} \cdot (\hat{\mathbf{S}} \times \vec{\epsilon}))] \quad (6.89)$$

The action of $\hat{\Phi}_r$ on the initial wave function gives the extra phase shift. P denotes the path order. Consider a circular path,

$$\hat{\Phi}_r = \exp\left[\frac{2i\Omega^2}{\hbar c^2} \mathbf{s} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{S}}\right] \quad (6.90)$$

If the spin is polarized perpendicular to the plane of symmetry, then the corresponding phase shift is,

$$\delta\theta = \frac{A\Omega^2}{c^2} \quad (6.91)$$

The phase shift obtained in equation 6.91 is small compared to the one in equation 6.66. The phase shift in equation 6.90 is similar to the phase shift due to the electromagnetic field, i.e., the Aharonov-Casher (AC) phase shift.

7. Spin Transport in Non-Inertial Frames

Spintronics is spin-based electronics, a branch of physics that studies the quantum transport properties of spin and has immense potential in technological applications. The main challenge here is the production and control of spin current, which is a non-conserved quantity. Nevertheless, the spin of the electron couples with other parameters, leading to Spin-Orbit coupling (SOC), Spin-rotation coupling (SOC), and Zeeman coupling. We have seen in Chapter 6 that the rotational frequency can be modified with momentum and time in rotating frames. Theoretically, such variation can alter the coupling terms and in turn the spin transport [8].

7.1 Generation of Spin Current in Non-Inertial Frames

Recently, it has been established that non-inertial fields can generate and control spin currents. Dirac equation in the presence of acceleration and rotation is given by the relation,

$$[i\gamma^\mu(x)(D_\mu + ie\mathbf{A}_\mu) - m]\Psi(x) = 0 \quad (7.1)$$

$$D_\mu = \partial_\mu + i\Gamma_\mu(x) \quad (7.2)$$

where D_μ is the covariant derivative. $\Gamma_\mu(x)$ are the spin connections containing the effect of rotation, Ω , and acceleration, \mathbf{a} . A_μ are the gauge fields. The transfer of angular momentum between an external non-inertial field and electron spins is studied using the spin current tensor, given by,

$$S^{\rho\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{4m} [(\partial^\rho)\sigma^{\mu\nu(x)}\Psi - \sigma^{\mu\nu(x)}(\partial^\rho\Psi)] \quad (7.3)$$

$$\sigma^{\mu\nu}(x) = \frac{i}{2}[\gamma^\mu, \gamma^\nu] \quad (7.4)$$

$$\gamma^\mu = e^\mu_\alpha(x)\gamma^\alpha \quad (7.5)$$

Consider a particle in a rotating frame, S' , which rotates about the \mathbf{z} axis with an angular velocity, $\vec{\Omega}$ w.r.t. a rest frame, S . In the rest frame of the particle, detailed calculation [10]

shows that,

$$\partial_i S^{i12} = \frac{(E+m)}{2E} \frac{\Omega a_2 x}{(1+\mathbf{a}\cdot\mathbf{x})} \quad (7.6)$$

$$\partial_i S^{i13} = \partial_i S^{i23} = 0 \quad (7.7)$$

$$\mathbf{a} = (a_1, a_2, a_3) \quad (7.8)$$

$$\vec{\Omega} = (0, 0, \Omega) \quad (7.9)$$

when $a_2 = 0$ and $\Omega = 0$, equation 7.6 becomes,

$$\partial_i S^{i12} = 0 \quad (7.10)$$

i.e., if there is no acceleration or if there is no rotation or in the absence of both, the spin current tensor is conserved in inertial frames.

Dirac's Hamiltonian in non-inertial frames is,

$$H = \beta m c^2 + c(\alpha \cdot p) + \frac{1}{2c} [(\mathbf{a}\cdot\mathbf{x})(p\cdot\vec{\alpha}) + (p\cdot\vec{\alpha})(\mathbf{a}\cdot\mathbf{x})] + \beta m(\mathbf{a}\cdot\mathbf{x}) - \vec{\Omega}(\mathbf{L} + \mathbf{S}) \quad (7.11)$$

where $\vec{\alpha}$ and $\vec{\Omega}$ are respectively the linear acceleration and the rotational frequency of the transformed frame w.r.t to the inertial frame S. \mathbf{L} and \mathbf{S} are respectively the orbital angular momentum and spin of the Dirac particles. β and α are Dirac matrices.

$$\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{x} \times \mathbf{p} \quad (7.12)$$

using the Foldy Wouthuysen Transformations (FWT) approach [12, 13] we can find the non-relativistic limit of equation 7.11. The Pauli Schrodinger Hamiltonian of a Dirac particle of positive energy and charge $-e$, in an inertial frame is given by,

$$H_{FW} = (m c^2 + \frac{p^2}{2m}) + m(\mathbf{a}\cdot\mathbf{x}) + \frac{\hbar}{4m c^2} \vec{\sigma}\cdot(\mathbf{a} \times \mathbf{p}) - \vec{\Omega}\cdot\mathbf{L} + \vec{\Omega}\cdot\mathbf{S} \quad (7.13)$$

In equation 7.13, the second term is the potential energy due to acceleration and the fourth term is the potential due to rotation.

$$\phi_a = -\frac{m}{e} \mathbf{a}\cdot\mathbf{x} \quad (7.14)$$

Acceleration-induced potential gives rise to an electric field, which has important contributions to the spin current and spin polarization. From equation 7.14. The electric field is given by the relation,

$$\mathbf{E}_a = \frac{m}{e} \mathbf{a} \quad (7.15)$$

From earlier discussions, the form of Gauge potential arising from the coupling between rotation and orbital angular momentum is,

$$\mathbf{A}_\Omega = \frac{mc}{e} (\vec{\omega} \times \mathbf{x}) \quad (7.16)$$

The magnetic field induced by the rotation of the Dirac particle of charge -e is,

$$\mathbf{B}_\Omega = \frac{2mc}{e} \vec{\Omega} \quad (7.17)$$

Substitute equations 7.14, 7.15, and 7.17 in equation 7.13.

$$H_{FW} = mc^2 + \frac{p^2}{2m} + -e\phi\mathbf{a} - \frac{\hbar e}{4m^2c^2} \vec{\sigma} \cdot (\mathbf{p} \times \mathbf{E}) - \vec{\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{L} + \frac{\hbar e}{4m} (\vec{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{B}) \quad (7.18)$$

We can omit mc^2 as it does not change the energy level difference and hence is not of any physical importance. The 4th term is the inertial spin-orbit coupling term. The 5th term denotes the coupling between orbital angular momentum and rotation. The last term is due to the spin rotation coupling term, i.e., the Zeeman-like coupling term.

The magnetic moment of the electron is,

$$\mu = \frac{e\hbar}{2mc} \quad (7.19)$$

Let us find the total potential on the inertial frame ϕ_I due to the Dirac particle which is accelerating and rotating. It should be expressed as a sum of potential due to rotation and acceleration,

$$\phi_I = e(\phi\mathbf{a} + \phi_\Omega) \quad (7.20)$$

where,

$$\phi_\Omega = \frac{m}{2e}(\vec{\Omega} \times \mathbf{x})^2 \quad (7.21)$$

Consider the equation,

$$H_{FW} = \frac{1}{2m}(p - \frac{e}{c}\mathbf{A}_\Omega - \frac{\mu}{2c}(\mathbf{E}_a \times \sigma)) - \phi_I - \frac{\mu}{2}\sigma \cdot \mathbf{B}_\Omega \quad (7.22)$$

Retaining the terms up to $\frac{1}{c^2}$ order, equation 7.22 takes the form of equation 7.18. This Hamiltonian has a $U(1) \otimes U(2)$ gauge symmetry. U(1) gauge potential and U(2) spin gauge potential are respectively given by,

$$A_\mu = (\phi_I, \mathbf{A}_\Omega) \quad (7.23)$$

$$b_\mu = (-\vec{\sigma} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{B}_\Omega}{2}, -\vec{\sigma} \times \frac{\mathbf{E}_a}{2}) \quad (7.24)$$

We get the 8×8 Kane Hamiltonian to be [13],

$$H_{8 \times 8} = \begin{pmatrix} (E_c + \phi)I_2 & \sqrt{3}PT.k & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}P\sigma.k \\ \sqrt{3}P \dagger T.k & (E_c + \phi)I_4 & 0 \\ -\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}P\sigma.k & 0 & (E_c - \Delta_0 + \phi)I_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (7.25)$$

where T matrices are given by,

$$T_x = \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} -\sqrt{3} & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & \sqrt{3} \end{pmatrix} \quad (7.26)$$

$$T_y = -i \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{3} & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \sqrt{3} \end{pmatrix} \quad (7.27)$$

$$T_z = -i \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (7.28)$$

i.e., equation 7.25 becomes,

$$H_{8 \times 8} = \begin{pmatrix} E_c + \phi_{tot} & 0 & -\frac{Pk_+}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{\sqrt{2}Pk_z}{\sqrt{3}} & \frac{Pk_-}{\sqrt{6}} & 0 & -\frac{Pk_z}{\sqrt{3}} & -\frac{Pk_-}{\sqrt{3}} \\ 0 & E_c + \phi_{tot} & 0 & -\frac{Pk_+}{\sqrt{6}} & \frac{\sqrt{2}Pk_z}{\sqrt{3}} & \frac{Pk_-}{\sqrt{2}} & -\frac{Pk_+}{\sqrt{3}} & \frac{Pk_z}{\sqrt{3}} \\ -\frac{Pk_-}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & E_v + \phi_{tot} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\sqrt{2}Pk_z}{\sqrt{3}} & -\frac{Pk_-}{\sqrt{6}} & 0 & E_v + \phi_{tot} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{Pk_+}{\sqrt{6}} & \frac{\sqrt{2}Pk_z}{\sqrt{3}} & 0 & 0 & E_v + \phi_{tot} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{Pk_+}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & E_v + \phi_{tot} & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{Pk_z}{\sqrt{3}} & -\frac{Pk_-}{\sqrt{3}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & E_v - \Delta_0 + \phi_{tot} & 0 \\ -\frac{Pk_+}{\sqrt{3}} & \frac{Pk_z}{\sqrt{3}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & E_v - \Delta_0 + \phi_{tot} \end{pmatrix} \quad (7.29)$$

E_c , E_v , $E_G = E_c - E_v$, Δ_0 , and P are the energy of the conduction band, the energy of the valence band, energy gap of the material, spin-orbit gap and Kane momentum respectively.

$$k_+ = \frac{k_x + k_y}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (7.30)$$

$$k_- = \frac{k_x - k_y}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (7.31)$$

Eliminating the valence band components from the Schrodinger equation, we get,

$$(T.k \frac{3p^2}{\tilde{E} - \phi + E_0} T^\dagger \cdot \mathbf{k} + \vec{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{k} \frac{3p^2}{E - \phi + E_0 + \Delta_0} \vec{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{k}) \psi_c = (\tilde{E} - \phi) \psi_c \quad (7.32)$$

where,

$$\tilde{E} = E - E_c \quad (7.33)$$

$$E_0 = E_c + k_v \quad (7.34)$$

Denominators are expanded to first order in $\frac{E-\phi}{E_0}$ and $\frac{E-\phi}{E_0+\Delta_0}$, and taking,

$$\tilde{\psi}_c = [1 + \frac{p^2}{12} (\frac{2k^2 - \frac{e}{\hbar} \vec{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{B}}{E_0}) + \frac{k^2 + \frac{e}{\hbar} \vec{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{B}}{E_0 + \Delta_0}] \quad (7.35)$$

Expanding the equation in terms of $\tilde{\psi}_c$,

$$\tilde{E} \tilde{\psi}_c = [l + n] \tilde{\psi}_c \quad (7.36)$$

$$l = \frac{pk^2}{3} \left(\frac{2}{E_0} + \frac{1}{E_0 + \Delta_0} \right) + \phi - \frac{p^2}{3} \left(\frac{1}{E_0} + \frac{1}{E_0 + \Delta_0} \right) \frac{e}{\hbar} \vec{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{B} \quad (7.37)$$

$$n = \frac{ep^2}{3} \left(\frac{1}{E_0^2} + \frac{1}{(E_0 + \Delta_0)^2} \right) \sigma \cdot (k \times \mathbf{E}) - \frac{ep^2}{6} \left(\frac{2}{E_0^2} + \frac{1}{(E_0 + \Delta_0)^2} \right) \nabla \cdot \mathcal{E} \quad (7.38)$$

The $k.p$ Hamiltonian of the conduction band electrons can be,

$$H_{k.p} = \frac{p^2 k^2}{3} \left(\frac{2}{E_0} + \frac{1}{E_0 + \Delta_0} \right) + e\phi - \frac{p^2}{3} \left(\frac{1}{E_0} + \frac{1}{E_0 + \Delta_0} \right) \frac{ie}{\hbar} \vec{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{B} + \frac{ep^2}{3} \left(\frac{1}{E_0^2} + \frac{1}{(E_0 + \Delta_0)^2} \right) (\sigma \cdot (\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{E}_{tot})) \quad (7.39)$$

The total inertial Hamiltonian, i.e., including the effects of acceleration of conduction band electrons is,

$$H_{tot} = \frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m^*} + e\phi + \left(1 + \frac{\delta g}{2} \right) \mu_B \vec{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{B} + e(\lambda + \delta\lambda) \vec{\sigma} \cdot (\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{E}_{tot}) \quad (7.40)$$

$$\frac{1}{m^*} = \frac{1}{m} + \frac{2p^2}{2\hbar^2} \left(\frac{2}{E_G} + \frac{1}{E_G + \Delta_0} \right) \quad (7.41)$$

$$\mathbf{E}_{tot} = -\nabla \phi_{tot} = \mathbf{E} - \mathbf{E}_{tot} \quad (7.42)$$

where λ is SOC strength in a vacuum.

$$\lambda = \frac{\hbar^2}{4m^2 c^2} \quad (7.43)$$

δg denotes the Zeeman coupling strength and $\delta\lambda$ is the renormalization SOC parameter, which appears due to the interband mixing in the $k.p$ perturbation theory.

$$\delta g = -\frac{4m p^2}{\hbar^2} \left(\frac{1}{E_G} - \frac{1}{(E_G + \Delta_0)} \right) \quad (7.44)$$

$$\delta\lambda = \frac{p^2}{3} \left(\frac{1}{E_0^2} - \frac{1}{(E_0 + \Delta_0)^2} \right) \quad (7.45)$$

The effective SOC term is,

$$\lambda_{eff} = \lambda + \delta\lambda \quad (7.46)$$

In the absence of rotation,

$$H = \frac{p^2}{2m} + e\phi - \frac{e}{\hbar}\lambda_{eff}\vec{\sigma}\cdot(\mathbf{E}_{tot} \times \mathbf{p}) \quad (7.47)$$

To find the semi-classical force equation,

$$F = m^*\ddot{x} = \frac{1}{i\hbar}[m^*\dot{x}, H] + m^*\frac{\dot{x}}{t} \quad (7.48)$$

where m^* is the effective mass. The second term in the RHS disappears only when $x = x(t)$. From equation 7.40 and the Heisenberg equation of motion, we obtain,

$$\dot{x} = \frac{\mathbf{P}}{m^*} - \lambda_{eff}\frac{e}{\hbar}(\sigma \times \mathbf{E}) \quad (7.49)$$

Using equations 7.40, 7.49, 7.48, and the Heisenberg equation, we obtain,

$$F = -e\phi_{tot} + \lambda_{eff}\frac{em^*}{\hbar}\dot{x} \times \nabla \times \sigma \times \mathbf{E} \quad (7.50)$$

Equation 7.50 is similar to the Lorentz force experienced by a charged particle of mass m^* , and charge e in an electromagnetic field. From analogy,

$$A_{eff} = \lambda_{eff}\frac{em^*}{\hbar}(\vec{\sigma} \times \mathbf{E}_{tot}) \quad (7.51)$$

Spin-dependent Lorentz force is responsible for the spin transport and spin hall effect of our inertial system.

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \frac{\mathbf{P}}{m} + v_{\vec{\sigma}}\mathbf{a} \quad (7.52)$$

$$v_{\vec{\sigma}}\mathbf{a} = -\lambda_{eff}\frac{e}{\hbar}(\vec{\sigma} \times \mathbf{E}_{tot}) \quad (7.53)$$

It is the spin-dependent anomalous velocity term which is a function of spin-orbit gap and band gap energy. When $\lambda_0 = 0$ or $\delta\lambda_0 = 0$, $v_{\vec{\sigma}}\mathbf{a} = 0$.

7.2 Spin Current and Spin Conductivity

The force term in equation 7.50 can be split into spin-independent and spin-dependent parts.

$$F = F_0 + F_\sigma \quad (7.54)$$

The potential can be expressed as the sum of applied external potential and lattice potential.

$$\phi = \phi_0 + \phi_l \quad (7.55)$$

Conductivity from the Drude model is given by,

$$\sigma_D = \frac{ne^2\tau}{m} \quad (7.56)$$

Let us assume τ to be independent of spin and electric field. Then,

$$j = \sigma_D \mathbf{E} \quad (7.57)$$

Current from $\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{p}$ perturbation theory, which can be expressed as a sum of spin-independent and spin-dependent, is given by the relation,

$$j_{\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{p}} = j_{\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{p}}^{0\mathbf{a}} + j_{\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{p}}^{\mathbf{sa}}(\vec{\sigma}) \quad (7.58)$$

$$j_{\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{p}}^{0\mathbf{a}} = \frac{e^2\rho\tau}{m^*}(E_0 - \mathbf{E}_a) \quad (7.59)$$

where \mathbf{E}_a is the fictitious field due to the acceleration of the frame.

$$j_{\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{p}}^{\mathbf{sa}} = \frac{m}{m^*}\left(1 + \frac{\delta\lambda}{\lambda}\right)j_{\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{p}}^{\mathbf{sa}}(\vec{\sigma}) \quad (7.60)$$

$$j_{\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{p}}^{\mathbf{sa}}(\vec{\sigma})(0) = \frac{\hbar e^3\tau^2 p\mu}{m^2\hbar}(n \times (\mathbf{E}_0 - \mathbf{E}_a)) \quad (7.61)$$

If we switch off the external fields,

$$j_{\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{p}}^{\mathbf{sa}} = -\frac{\hbar e^3\tau^2 p\mu}{m^2\hbar}(n \times \mathbf{E}_a) = -\sigma_{H\phi}^{\mathbf{s}\mathbf{a}}(n \times \mathbf{E}_a) \quad (7.62)$$

$-\sigma_{H\phi}^{\mathbf{s}\mathbf{a}}$ is the spin Hall conductivity. i.e., with an increasing acceleration of the field, we can increase \mathbf{E}_z , which produces a long spin hall effect.

7.3 Spin Filter Formation

When acceleration is along \mathbf{z} direction and an external magnetic field is present, from equation 7.40, we can obtain,

$$H = \frac{\pi^2}{2m^*} + \frac{e\alpha_{eff}}{\hbar}(\pi_x\sigma - y - \pi_y\sigma_x) \quad (7.63)$$

$$\alpha_{eff} =_{eff} E_z \quad (7.64)$$

This is the Rashba-like coupling that contains the effect of acceleration and $k.p$ parameter.

$$\vec{\pi} = \mathbf{p} - e\mathbf{A} \quad (7.65)$$

Define, to the second order

$$\mathbf{A}' = \frac{c}{2}(-\sigma_y, \sigma_x, 0) \quad (7.66)$$

$$q = \frac{2m^* \alpha_{eff}}{\hbar} \quad (7.67)$$

$$\tilde{A} = e\mathbf{A} + q\mathbf{A} \quad (7.68)$$

Equation 7.63 can be written as,

$$H = \frac{1}{2m^*} \left(p - \frac{\tilde{e}}{c} \tilde{A} \right)^2 \quad (7.69)$$

where \tilde{e} is the coupling constant which equals to unity.

The berry curvature is defined as,

$$\Omega_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_\nu - \partial_\nu \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_\mu - \frac{ie}{c\hbar} [\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_m u, \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_n u] \quad (7.70)$$

where the \mathbf{z} component of this field,

$$\Omega_z = \Omega_{xy} = e\mathbf{B}_z + q^2 \frac{c}{2\hbar} \sigma_z \quad (7.71)$$

The first term in equation 7.71 is the reason behind the AB phase. The second term in equation 7.71 is due to spin-orbit coupling, which has opposite signs for the spin up and spin down

respectively. i.e., opposite spins experience opposite vertical magnetic fields and carry equal and opposite AC phase,

$$\theta_{AC} = \oint \vec{dx} \cdot \mathbf{A}(x, \vec{\sigma}) \quad (7.72)$$

$$\Omega_z = e \frac{\phi_B}{W} + q \frac{\phi_I}{W} \quad (7.73)$$

Flux due to the external field which is responsible for AB phase shift is,

$$\phi_B = B_z W \quad (7.74)$$

The physical field arising due to the inertial SOC effect which is responsible for AC phase shift is,

$$\phi_I = \sigma_z W q \frac{c}{2\hbar} \quad (7.75)$$

These two phase shifts act as a filter for spin-up and down electrons.

7.4 Induced Spin-Orbit Coupling

From equation 7.11, by considering solely the effect of rotation in the presence of an external magnetic field, i.e., by putting $\mathbf{a} = 0$, we obtain,

$$H_\Omega = \frac{\pi_\Omega^2}{2m} - e\phi_\Omega - \mu\vec{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{B} - \frac{\hbar}{2}\vec{\sigma} \cdot \vec{\Omega} \quad (7.76)$$

where,

$$\pi_\Omega = \mathbf{p} - e\mathbf{A}' \quad (7.77)$$

$$A' = A + A_\Omega \quad (7.78)$$

For the choice of,

$$A_\Omega = \frac{m}{e}(\vec{\Omega} \times \mathbf{x}) \quad (7.79)$$

we calculated the rotation-induced magnetic field, which is given by,

$$B_\Omega = \frac{2m\vec{\Omega}}{e} \quad (7.80)$$

$$\phi_\Omega = \frac{m}{2e}(\vec{\Omega} \times \mathbf{x})^2 \quad (7.81)$$

i.e., equation 7.76 further reduces to the form,

$$H_\Omega = \frac{\pi_\Omega^2}{2m} - e\phi_\Omega - \mu\vec{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{B} - \frac{\mu_B}{2}\vec{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{B}_\Omega \quad (7.82)$$

The last term in equation 7.82 is the Spin Rotation coupling term. The third term denotes the interaction between the magnetic field and spin.

Let us consider planar rotation in the momentum space about the axis of the induced \mathbf{B} .

$$\Omega = |\Omega|\hat{n}(k_\Omega, t) \quad (7.83)$$

$$\vec{k}_\Omega = \frac{1}{|k|}(k_{\Omega x}, -k_{\Omega y}, 0) \quad (7.84)$$

$$|k| = \sqrt{k_{\Omega x}^2 + k_{\Omega y}^2} \quad (7.85)$$

Thus equation 7.82 becomes,

$$H_\Omega = \frac{\pi_\Omega^2}{2m} - e\phi_\Omega - \mu\vec{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{B} - B_\Omega(\sigma_y p_{y\Omega} - \sigma_x p_{x\Omega}) \quad (7.86)$$

where the Dresselhaus coupling parameter is,

$$B_\Omega = \frac{1}{2} \frac{|\Omega|}{|k|} \quad (7.87)$$

If the frame is accelerated in the \mathbf{z} direction, we will get a contribution from $\vec{\sigma} \cdot (\mathbf{p} \times \mathbf{E}_a)$, equation 7.86 and equation 7.63 as,

$$H = \frac{\pi_\Omega^2}{2m} + \alpha_a(k_{\Omega x}\sigma_y - k_{\Omega y}\sigma_x) - B_\Omega(\sigma_y p_{y\Omega} - \sigma_x p_{x\Omega}) \quad (7.88)$$

where, Rashba-like coupling factor is,

$$\alpha_a = \lambda E_a \quad (7.89)$$

8. Conclusion

By exploring the quantum mechanical description of various systems in non-inertial frames, this review gave us some subtle insights into the connections between systems in inertial and non-inertial frames. First of all, depending on the particular coordinate transformation, we observed there can be covariance or invariance between the Schrodinger equation derived in the respective frames. This is achieved using a suitable gauge transformation of the wave function which is specific to the coordinate transformation undergone by the particular frame.

We have also examined the variation in the associated physical parameters of the system in these respective frames. They are observed to change or not depending on the coordinate transformation and the selected gauge transformation. Additionally, we compared the quantum mechanical pictures with the classical descriptions of the systems. There is a relation between the action in the classical treatment of non-inertial frames and the phase factor of gauge transformation of the wave function.

By looking at the transformation in the case of a quantum Harmonic Oscillator system alone, we could solve some initial value problems. This is attained by using Harmonic Oscillator-Harmonic Oscillator equivalence, Harmonic Oscillator-Free Particle Equivalence, and Free Particle-Free Particle equivalence. Though the Schrodinger equation remains intact in form, certain phase shifts emerge in the system's quantum mechanical description in the non-inertial frames. This is due to the terms present in the effective potential that arises in the non-inertial frames. These phase shifts are found to be quite promising in controlling the spin of the particles and have applications in Spintronics.

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Bibliography

1. Aharonov Bohm phase

It is the coupling between the complex phase and the EM potential which causes the particle to attain a phase difference in a region where $\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{B} = 0$. The phase shift obtained through Aharonov Bohm effect, ϕ_{AB} , is given as,

$$\phi_{AB} = \frac{q}{\hbar} \int \mathbf{A} \cdot d\vec{x} \quad (9.1)$$

2. Aharonov Casher Phase

This effect involves the interaction of the magnetic moment of a charged particle with an electric field. A travelling magnetic dipole is affected by an E and the interference brings a phase shift in the wave function of the particle, ϕ_{AC} , given by the relation,

$$\phi_{AC} = \frac{1}{\hbar c^2} \int (\mathbf{E} \times \vec{\mu}) \cdot d\vec{x} \quad (9.2)$$

3. Dresselhaus Coupling

Splitting of energy bands due to relativistic spin-orbit coupling. The Dresselhaus coupling can influence spin transport properties, such as spin relaxation times and spin diffusion lengths, which are important in spintronics applications.

4. Foldy Wouthuysen Transformations

The Foldy-Wouthuysen transformation is a technique to simplify the Hamiltonian in relativistic limits. By omitting relativistic interaction terms, the Foldy-Wouthuysen Hamiltonian retain key relativistic effects while still being tractable within a non-relativistic framework.

5. Rashba Coupling

Momentum-dependent splitting of spin bands due to spin-orbit interaction and asymmetry of the crystal potential. Rashba Hamiltonian is given by,

$$H_R = -\alpha_R(\vec{\sigma} \times p) \cdot \hat{z} \quad (9.3)$$

$$\alpha_R = -\frac{g\mu_B E_0}{2mc^2} \quad (9.4)$$

6. Spin Filter

Devices or materials that allow particles with certain spin orientations to pass through. Magnetic materials, spin-selective tunnelling, and semiconductor structures, among others, are used to attain such properties. They are quite useful in producing and controlling spin-polarized currents.

7. Spin Galvanic Effect

Generation of a spin polarization perpendicular to an applied electric current in certain materials with strong spin-orbit coupling. This phenomenon is used in Spintronics to generate and manipulate spin polarization using electrical currents.

8. Spin Hall Effect

This is a phenomenon where an electric current flowing through a material induces a transverse spin current perpendicular to the direction of the charge current due to spin-orbit coupling in the material. This effect is used to separate up and down spin electrons in Spintronics. The spin current density (J_s) induced by an applied electric field (\mathbf{E}) can be expressed as,

$$J_s = \sigma_{SH} \cdot (\mathbf{E} \times \hat{z}) \quad (9.5)$$

where, σ_{SH} is the spin hall conductivity tensor.

9. Spin Rotation Coupling

The Spin Rotation Coupling (SRC) or Sagnac M Ashhoon Phase refers to the interaction between the intrinsic spin of a particle and its motion under the influence of an external rotation. The Hamiltonian can be expressed as follows,

$$H_{SRC} = \frac{\vec{\mu} \cdot \vec{\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{S}}{2} \quad (9.6)$$

where μ is the magnetic moment of the particle, \mathbf{S} is the spin operator, and $\vec{\Omega}$ is the angular velocity of the rotating frame.

Reference

1. The equivalence principle and quantum mechanics by C.J Eliezer and P.G. Leach, 1977, American Journal of Physics, Vol. 45, P-1218.
2. The Galilean covariance of quantum mechanics in the case of external fields by Harvey R. Brown and Peter R. Holland, 1999, American Journal of Physics, Vol. 67, P-204.
3. Einstein's equivalence principle in quantum mechanics revisited by Micheal Naunberg, 2016, American Journal of Physics, Vol. 84, P-879.
4. Quantum dynamics and non-inertial frames of reference. I: Generality by Shin Takagi, 1991, Progress of Theoretical Physics, Vol. 85, P-463.
5. Quantum Dynamics and non-inertial frames of reference. II: Harmonic Oscillator by Shin Takagi, 1991, Progress of Theoretical Physics, Vol. 85, P-723.
6. Quantum Dynamics in non-inertial frames of reference. III: Charged particles in time-dependent electromagnetic field by Shin Takagi, 1991, Progress of Theoretical Physics, Vol. 86, P-783.
7. Quantum mechanics in rotating frames by Jeeva Anandan, 2003, arXiv:quant-ph/0305081.
8. Spin transport in non-inertial frames by Debashree Chowdhury and B. Basu, 2014, Physica B: Condensed Matter, Vol. 448, P-155.
9. Quantum Field Theory by Lewis H. Ryder, 1985, Cambridge University Press.
10. Spin currents in non-inertial frames by G. Papini, 2013, Physics Letters A, Vol. 377, p-960.
11. Inertial effects of a Dirac particle, F. W. Hehl and Wei Tou Ni, 1990, Physics Review. D 42, p-2045.
12. Relativistic Quantum Mechanics. Wave Equations by Walter Greiner, 1981, Springer Berlin.
13. On the Dirac theory of spin 1/2 particles and its non-relativistic limit, L.L. Foldy and S Wouthuysen, 1950, Physics Review, Vol. 78, p-29.
14. Spin-Orbit Coupling effects in two-dimensional electron and hole system by Roland WringleR, 2003, Springer, Berlin.